

THE ROLE OF WILLPOWER QUALITIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SELF

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the role of willpower action in the development of future educators self-confidence, as well as the pathways to achieving goals and the direct contribution to the realization of clear desires and aspirations.*

Keywords: *educator, self-confidence, willpower qualities, motivation, self-regulation, self-defense, self-awareness.*

The beginning of the willpower act in individuals truly finds its expression in a rational, purposeful decision regarding how to achieve goals, and in the fact that the paths to achieving these goals directly serve the realization of specific desires and aspirations. Data analysis shows that when a well-founded decision is made about the chosen and selected actions being effective, productive, and convenient for use, and the alignment with the goal is based on reliable evidence and factors, then this process occurs without significant difficulties. Nevertheless, in most cases, the decision-making process, the decision about choice, and the creation of a success mechanism turn into a complex process, resulting in a struggle of motives. Therefore, the processes of selection and achieving consensus are considerably prolonged. For example, if an individual has developed a desire to change jobs, other aspirations with different characteristics will dominate. They can also hinder the intention to change the workplace. In particular, although the desire to change jobs is related to the fact that the salary at the new workplace is slightly higher, it also requires adaptation to a new social environment, a heterogeneous team, unfamiliar conditions, and different requirements. As a result of such relationships, a struggle of motives arises, based on:

- a) the need to give up the new job;
- b) the need to give up the feeling of internal satisfaction;
- c) the emergence of a valuable opportunity;
- d) the need to turn away from other needs for the sake of its prospects. In the struggle of motives, reflections may arise regarding whether to approve, acknowledge, or disapprove of the acceptance of any decision, as well as the fact that the struggle of motives may lead to the application of contradictory and mutually exclusive actions, not limited to just their analysis and evaluation.

As a result of the struggle between motives, the process of arriving at a specific decision or making a choice manifests itself, during which qualities such as doubt, lethargy, indifference, and indecision are expelled from the sphere of activity, and all attention is focused on implementing the decision and its execution. If after the decision has been made, cowardice continues to lead a person toward indecision, then willpower actions reflect a lack of zeal, determination, steadfastness, and striving toward the set goal. The individual prepares themselves mentally to achieve the goal, conducts a comparative analysis of information regarding the discrepancies between psychological and statistical expectations, and generalizes them [1].

Such an attitude (necessity) aimed at overcoming internal contradictions is, firstly, linked to certain desires of the subject, entrenched negative habits (which have turned into dynamic

stereotypes); secondly, a sense of adaptation to social life events; and thirdly, the struggle against disapproved moral and ethical principles, traditions, is directly governed by the willpower exertion, which has a unique characteristic of willpower action (regulatory function).

In social life, there are attempts to diminish the power of strong and determined aspirations that arise in human psyche. However, the very understanding of the possibility for the accepted decision to meet moral standards and principles of conduct holds social, socio-psychological, and universal psychological significance; it does not serve as a sufficiently strong factor to shift the individual from the "dead" point, as the functional system has weakened [2].

If the situation discussed above is understood by the individual as a social and personal duty, responsibility, accountability, determination, and perseverance, and if necessary stable internal experiences (regulatory feelings) are strengthened, then in such a situation, this leads to a genuine willpower effort that allows for the loss, weakening, and diminishing of aspirations. High feelings (duty, responsibility, accountability, patriotism, selflessness, etc.) reflect that moral and spiritual demands have become internalized, meaning they are transitioning into the individual's spiritual wealth, and the contradictions that arise between egoistic aspirations and altruistic desires in extraordinary situations have become the internal mechanisms of behavior. High feelings determine whether the struggle of motives will lean to the right or left and perform a regulatory function in ensuring the achievement of the goal. Only after conducting additional research in this area can one confidently and assertively express opinions about reality.

When discussing the volitional act in psychology, it is particularly emphasized that the internal mechanism of willpower effort manifests not only in the decision-making process but also during the execution phase when achieving high rates. The overall psychological significance of this is that the implementation of the accepted decision (execution) often encounters a variety of subjective and objective contradictions and difficulties, and overcoming them requires willpower effort and a state of tension [3].

As a result of the internal psychological struggle of the individual, if success is achieved, positive emotional experiences arise, such as the feeling of dominance over oneself, confidence in one's abilities, self-understanding, the ability to give oneself commands, self-control, and the awareness of the possibility of achieving the most important goals set before oneself (cognitive phenomenon). It is known that personal inclinations, general psychological attitudes (referred to as "Установка" in Russian), the influence of social attitudes (referred to as "Влияние" in Russian), and the adequately formed evaluation system based on one's role and status have particular significance in human development [4].

The analysis of quantitative results shows that willpower effort, which possesses specific characteristics for volitional actions, manifests not only due to the emergence of opposing states in the struggle of motives but also solely through overcoming objective difficulties in the process of executing the decision made by the individual. The analysis of the structure of the act of will demonstrates that this mental state allows for the explanation and interpretation of many characteristics of volitional activity. It is pertinent to note that volitional activity performs certain priority functions in the actions of the individual. These functions, first, enhance the qualitative level of the application of individual actions in practice; second, they create conditions for finding solutions to various problems that are of significant importance for a person's life and personal activity; third, they ensure the individual's penetration into the essence of the problem; and fourth, they serve to align the action of the volitional act with the goal [5]. Thus, the events that directly

trigger the volitional actions of the individual emphasize integrity, dynamism, the relative specificity of the psyche, individual selfhood, and the unity of experience and behavior, which should be given special attention. It is important to note that by observing these characteristics, we can see that they are not only interconnected but also capable of complementing each other. Within the framework of a systemic approach, one can encounter another interesting classification in the research of V.A. Gantzen.

Psychic States	Manifestation of Psychophysiological Characteristics
Motivation of Volitional States (tension – relaxation):	Positive (inspiration, determination, optimism, readiness, preparedness, set, activation)
	Organic (hypoxia, fatigue, hunger, sexual tension)
Affective States ("pleasure-displeasure"):	Positive (joy, friendship, love, harmony)
	Negative (antipathy, resentment, enmity, hatred, anger)
Attention in Conscious States:	Distraction, concentration, extreme degree of protection or hyperprotection

The aforementioned scientific observations from all authors who approach the process of developing self-confidence from a general psychological and psychophysiological perspective have important significance for studying and analyzing social and psychological factors. From this viewpoint, it is appropriate to consider the process of developing self-confidence in modern students as a unique social-psychological phenomenon for study and research. Since the development of each individual or their ability to manage themselves at a literary level requires the investigation of a certain level of influencing social and psychological factors.

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